

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ECO-FRIENDLY CFF/PLA BIOCOMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

Chicken feather fiber (CFF) was mixed with poly(lactic) acid (PLA) to fabricate a new kind of biocomposite. Fibers from two different parts of chicken feather were used as reinforcement to the polymer matrix. The mechanical properties of CFF/PLA biocomposite samples processed with a twin-screw extruder and injection moulder were examined.

Keywords: Biocomposites, Chicken feather fiber, Poly(lactic) acid, Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Global warming and more frequent occurrences of natural disasters, such as earthquakes and tsunami, are calling for our awareness to environmental protection. Problems arise as human beings excessively exploit the earth's limited resources, while unwanted products are being disposed of continually. One of the effective measures is to turn what we consider as 'trash' into useful resources. In order to tackle the land pollution problem, it is also recommended to make use of bio-degradable materials whenever possible. Driven by these two concepts for environmental protection, an eco-friendly biocomposite fabricated with biodegradable poly(lactic) acid and chicken feather fiber was developed and examined.

MATRIX AND REINFORCEMENT

Poly(lactic) acid (PLA)

PLA is a thermoplastic polymer with can be synthesized by condensation of lactic acid or ring opening polymerization of lactide which is the diester of lactic acid [1]. Due to its good biocompatibility, biodegradability, mechanical properties and light weight, PLA has been widely used in many aspects, such as medical applications [2, 3] and automotive parts [4]. The commercial market for PLA has increased substantially in recent years. PLA offers the advantages of relatively high strength and ability to be processed in most equipment, but reinforcement is usually needed for practical

applications due to its brittleness [5, 6]. The addition of filler materials or fibers is an effective way to improve the mechanical and thermal properties of PLA. Traditional fibers (e.g. glass fiber and recycled newspaper fiber) and natural fibers (e.g. bamboo and silk fibers) have been used as reinforcements to enhance the mechanical properties of PLA [7, 8]. In this paper, the feasibility and performance of using chicken feather fiber as reinforcement for PLA will be studied.

Chicken feather fiber (CFF)

Chicken feather is generated and treated as a waste product in the poultry sector. Approximately 2×10^9 kg of chicken feather is being disposed of in the United States every year [9], which has created a massive source of solid waste. Chicken feather fiber (CFF) consists of hydrophobic keratin, a protein having similar strength as nylon but with a diameter smaller than that of wood fiber. One surprisingly important feature of CFF is the special semi-crystalline and cross-linked structure, which enhances the resistance of polymer-based composites to mechanical stress and provides a relatively high elastic modulus of about 3.4 - 5 GPa [10]. CFF has a high aspect ratio, and is durable, renewable and environmentally-friendly. All of the afore-mentioned good properties contribute to the promising advantage of using CFF as polymer reinforcement.

The chicken feather used in this study was obtained from a company in mainland China. A photograph of the chicken feather is shown in Fig. 1. The stiff central core of the feather is called the quill, and the strands of material that emerge from it are known as barbs. The barbs at one end of the feather are firm, compact, and closely knit, while those at the other end are downy, i.e. soft, loose, and fluffy. The down feather provides insulation, and the flight feather provides an airfoil, protects the body from moisture, the skin from injury, and colors and shapes for displays. [11]

Figure 1. Photograph of a chicken feather.

EXPERIMENTS

Fabrication of CFF/PLA biocomposites

The chicken feather was first immersed in alcohol for 24 hours, washed in a water soluble organic solvent, and dried under 60 °C for another 24 hours. The barbs of the feather were then separated from the quill manually, and the length was controlled within 10 - 30 mm. Two types of fibers, flight feather fiber and down feather fiber, can be obtained from different regions of a single chicken feather as mentioned, and they were then used as reinforcements for PLA matrix.

PLA pellets from Natureworks were used as the polymeric matrix in this study. The pellets underwent dry treatment in an oven with heat applied at 80 °C for 24 h to remove excessive moisture before the molding of the composite samples.

All CFF/PLA biocomposite samples were prepared by extrusion and injection molding method. The weight content of CFF varied from 2 % to 10 %. PLA pellets and CFF were fed into a Hakke MiniLab twin-screw micro extruder, and a uniform temperature of 180 °C was maintained at all zones inside the machine. The screw speed and the mixing duration were set to be 100 rpm and 10 min respectively. A Thermo Hakke small scale injection molding machine was used to produce dumbbell-shape composite samples. The injection cylinder and the mold were preheated to desired temperatures of 200 °C and 45 °C respectively, and the molten mixture from the micro extruder was then transferred to the injection molding machine. The shape of molded samples was in accordance with ASTM D638. Fig. 2 shows the PLA sample (top) and the CFF/PLA biocomposite samples fabricated with 5 wt% of down feather fiber (middle) and flight feather fiber (bottom), respectively. The PLA sample is transparent in color, which is the same as the pellets before injection molding, and the CFF/PLA biocomposites have shades of yellowish brown.

Figure 2. PLA sample (top) and CFF/PLA biocomposites with 5 wt% of down feather fiber (middle) and flight feather fiber (bottom).

Experimental procedures

Tensile tests were conducted to compare the mechanical properties of pure PLA and CFF/PLA biocomposite samples according to the ASTM standard. A 50-kN MTS

Alliance RT-50 tensile machine and an extensometer were used. The span length of every sample was 25 mm, and the crosshead speed with a loading rate of 1 mm/min was employed. Stress-strain curves of the test samples with different weight contents of CFF were obtained, from which the tensile properties were deduced. After the mechanical property test, microscopic analysis was conducted with Leica Stereoscan 440 scanning electron microscope (SEM) on the fracture surfaces of the samples to examine the failure surface structure and failure behavior induced by tensile test.

Dynamic storage modulus (E') and mechanical $\tan \delta$ were measured by a dynamic mechanical analyzer (Perkin-Elmer Diamond DMA Lab System) at different temperatures ranging from 25 °C to 140 °C. A heating rate of 2 °C/min, an original length of 50 mm and a frequency of 2 Hz were set as the conditions for the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Flight feather fiber vs. down feather fiber

As aforementioned, two kinds of CFF – the flight feather fiber and the down feather fiber were obtained from the chicken feather. Figs. 3(a) and (b) show the images of the cross-section of these two kinds of fibers captured with a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The fibers are cylindrical in shape. The diameter of flight feather fiber (Fig. 3(a)) is about 5 times to that of the down feather fiber (Fig. 3(b)). The former has a hollow cross-section, while the latter has a solid core, with little protrusions at certain intervals along its length.

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of (a) flight feather fiber and (b) down feather fiber.

CFF/PLA biocomposites were fabricated with these two types of CFF, and the CFF content was fixed at 5 wt%. The results of tensile test conducted with the two sets of samples are compared with that of pure PLA sample and listed in Table 1. As seen from the data, the tensile strength of PLA decreases when CFF is added. The decrease of strength in polymer reinforced by natural fiber has also been reported by other researchers [1, 8]. The decrement is within 7 MPa for the biocomposite sample with 5

wt% of down feather fiber, but the Young's modulus of this set of sample has increased by 16%. For the CFF/PLA biocomposite sample with 5 wt% of flight feather fiber, both the peak stress and Young's modulus have decreased. Judging from the physical structures of these two types of fibers as shown in Fig. 3, and confirmed by the experimental results, the down feather fiber is demonstrated to perform better as reinforcement to PLA. Therefore, CFF/PLA biocomposite samples for subsequent experiments have been prepared solely with down feather fiber which is denoted by CFF unless otherwise stated.

Table 1. Tensile strength and Young's modulus of PLA sample and 5 wt% CFF/PLA biocomposites

Samples	Peak stress (MPa)	Young's modulus (MPa)
Pure PLA	61.65	3620
CFF/PLA (with flight feather fiber)	49.4	3492
CFF/PLA (with down feather fiber)	55.02	4184

CFF/PLA biocomposites with different fiber contents

CFF/PLA biocomposite samples with different fiber weight percentages were fabricated and tested. The Young's moduli of the samples, which have been deduced from the stress-strain curves of the tensile test, are plotted in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Tensile properties of CFF/PLA biocomposites.

It is found that the tensile modulus of every CFF/PLA biocomposite sample in our experiment is higher than that of pure PLA sample. A maximum value of 4.2 GPa (increment of 16 %) is reached for the CFF/PLA biocomposite sample with CFF content of 5 wt%. The values of elongation at break are also shown in Fig. 4 for comparison. With the addition of 2 wt% of CFF, the elongation at break has increased by 56 %. It implies that the ductility of PLA matrix was effectively improved by the incorporation of a small amount of CFF, which is within 8 wt% in this case. The CFFs are believed to act as bridges to prolong the fracture process of the CFF/PLA biocomposite. In other words, the failure of the biocomposite is dependent on the bridging effect of CFFs inside the composite, and the risk of sudden failure can be reduced with higher ductility. In the course of our experiments, when the CFF content was over 10 %, the sample became brittle and was not able to be removed intact from the mold.

SEM observation

The morphology of fracture surfaces of CFF/PLA specimens was investigated by SEM, and the micrographs in different magnification for the composite sample with 5 wt% of CFF content are shown in Figs. 5(a) and (b). It can be observed in Fig. 5(a) that the fibers have been separated from each other during extrusion process and were well-dispersed in the PLA matrix. Few voids are found on the fracture surface, as the fibers are trapped by the PLA matrix. A network has been formed by CFFs inside the biocomposite as reinforcement during loading condition (pointed by the arrows in the figure). The bridging effect can prevent crack propagation and enable effective stress transfer between the matrix and the fibers, leading to a better mechanical tensile property. It is also noticed in Fig. 5(b) that most of the fibers were broken off together with PLA matrix, instead of being drawn out. There is good adhesion between CFF and PLA matrix.

Figure 5. SEM images for fracture surfaces of CFF/PLA biocomposite with 5 wt% of CFF content.

3.2. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

DMA was performed to examine how the stiffness of CFF/PLA biocomposites is affected when exposed to elevated temperature. The dynamic storage moduli (E') for pure PLA and CFF/PLA biocomposites with different weight contents are compared in Fig. 6. The test temperature increased gradually from 25 °C to 140 °C. It is seen from this figure that pure PLA has a much lower E' than CFF/PLA samples at ambient temperature. The values of E' for CFF/PLA samples increase with the gradual addition of CFF, and reach a maximum gain of 73% when compared to pure PLA. It is demonstrated that the addition of CFF has improved the stiffness of PLA. In this analysis, the stress can be transferred from PLA matrix to CFFs, so the mobility and deformation of the matrix is reduced.

Figure 6. Storage modulus as a function of temperature for PLA and CFF/PLA biocomposites.

Tangent delta ($\tan \delta$) is a function of temperature which is given by:

$$\tan \delta = E'' / E' \quad (1)$$

where E'' is the loss modulus. A comparison of tangent delta for pure PLA and CFF/PLA biocomposites is shown in Fig. 7. The glass transition temperature (T_g) can be deduced from the peak of $\tan \delta$ curve. It is found from Fig. 7 that pure PLA has a T_g of 65.1 °C, and the T_g of CFF/PLA biocomposites are 64.5, 64.8, 65.2 and 66.3 °C, respectively, for different CFF contents ranging from 2 wt% to 10 wt%. No appreciable change in $\tan \delta$ values is observed. It is highlighted that the introduction of CFF into PLA matrix has reduced the value of $\tan \delta$, which is in agreement with the results from previous literature [12]. Generally, the damping in the transition region measures the imperfection in the elasticity and that much of the energy used to deform a material during DMA testing is dissipated directly into heat. Hence, the mobility of the biocomposites decreases and the mechanical loss to overcome inter-friction between molecular chains is reduced in the presence of CFF.

Figure 7. Tangent delta as a function of temperature for PLA and CFF/PLA biocomposites.

CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility of using chicken feather fiber to reinforce PLA has been explored in this paper. Flight feather fiber and down feather fiber were separated from chicken feather, and were added to the PLA matrix respectively. The fibers were well-dispersed in the PLA matrix as seen from the SEM photographs. It was found that the down feather fiber was able to improve the stiffness of PLA. Different CFF content (2 wt% - 10 wt%) has been attempted in this study, and the maximum increase of Young's modulus was achieved with the addition of 5 wt% of CFF. The increase in ductility of the biocomposites with a small amount of CFF was able to reduce the risk of sudden failure as the fracture process has been prolonged. From the DMA results, incorporation of CFFs caused a considerable increase of the storage modulus (stiffness) and a decrease of the $\tan \delta$ values. In the next stage of study, focus will be put on the improvement of interfacial bonding and the evaluation of the biodegradability of CFF/PLA biocomposites.

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